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**EFFECTIVENESS OF CONTENT BASED INSTRUCTION AND LANGUAGE
DEVELOPMENT OF VIII STANDARD STUDENTS**

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EFFECTIVENESS OF CONTENT BASED INSTRUCTION AND LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT OF VIII STANDARD STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study focused on the Effectiveness of content based instruction and language development of VIII standard students. The method adopted for the present study is experimental study. Sample for the present study is VIII standard students from Government Higher Secondary School Sarkar Kollapatti at salem district. There were 60 students in total (30 students in experimental group and 30 students control group). In content based instruction, Theme based model is used for the present study. Simplified lesson plan, content oriented learning materials and language games and songs were taught by the investigator for the treatment of experimental group.50 objective type questions prepared from the content to test the Effectiveness of content based instruction.

Keywords: Content Based Instruction ,language development, models of CBI, sample.

Introduction

“Learning another language is like becoming another person”

-Haruki Murakami.

Language is very important in any type of communication. Because it expresses our opinions, feelings towards others. Developing language skills from childhood makes an individual to be good at language. In second language learning, classroom it is always a difficult task for the students to learn the language. The phobia of learning a second language is never ends. Students always have a negative opinion of learning a new language. Especially in schools students suffer difficult to make a sentence or to construct a sentence with certain grammar rules and regulations need to be learned. When we look into communicative approach the students became free to talk and learn the language. For learning a language there are number of approaches and methods are available. As the scenario changes teaching learning methods changes. To make it simple and make the language learning easier this Content-Based Instruction is much helpful for the students.

Review Of Related Literature

Vanichvasin, Patchara (2019)assessed the Effects of Content-Based Instruction on English Language Performance of Thai Undergraduate Students in a Non-English Program. The sample group was nineteen Thai UG students. The findings of the study is content-based instruction created positive results and could be used as an effective methodology and essential aid in engendering opportunities to use English, which resulted in increased English language performance.

Jaelani, and Selamat Riadi (2017) studied the Treating of Content-Based Instruction to Teach Writing Viewed from EFL Learners' Creativity. The research method of this research was quasi-experimental research. The techniques of collecting data were creativity test and writing test given to the both classes. The data were analyzed by using Multifactor Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test of 2×2 and Turkey test. The results revealed that Content-Based Instruction was more operational than Problem-based learning to teach writing.

Content-Based Instruction

Content-based instruction is an approach to language teaching that focuses not only the language itself, but rather on what is being taught through the language; that is, the language becomes the medium through which something new is learned. The principles of content based instruction are heavily rooted on the principles of communicative language teaching since they involve an active participation of students in the exchange of content. Since CBI in language learning plays crucial part in language as well as content learning the components of CBI are ever growing models. The Sheltered Model: It is mostly used at university where the goal of teachers is to enable their ESL students to study the same content material as regular English L1 students. Sheltered CBI is called “sheltered” because learners are given special assistance to help them understand regular classes. The Adjunct Model: Undertaken by ESL teachers. The aim of Adjunct classes is to prepare students for “mainstream” classes where they will join English L1 learners. The Theme Based Model: These classes can be taught by EFL teachers who create content material based on the needs and interests of the students. The model adopted for the present study is theme based model.

The Theme Based Model

Theme Based learning enables students to gain deep understanding for practical learning. That is topic is selected by the interest of student from that they will learn different facts about a particular topic. For example in this study researcher took unit 2, prose lesson about Sir Issac Newton in VIII standard English Content. The theme of the prose is learning about Issac Newton. The given prose is in past tense, and direct speech. The students directly learn the past tense and direct speech from the lesson as well they learn more about the inventions of Newton and the Laws he created.

To make learning more interesting video clippings were played and past tense songs were taught by the researcher to the experimental group in addition to that Newtons inventions were prepared as album by the investigator and handouts, board activity were given to the students. On the other hand there is no treatment given to the control group students. The experimental group students expand interest on language learning and they gain long time retention of content.

Operational Definitions

CBI : Content Based Instruction is a simplest way of teaching the content with the help of second language. This content based instruction combines three models of teaching

and learning. Content based instruction reduces the burden and phobia of second language learning.

Theme based model: Theme Based Model of teaching is one of the best way for teachers to gain the attention of students towards learning. This model captures the interest of students and kindles their thoughts and helps them to come up with their own creative ideas. It is the best model in CBI especially for the school students.

VIII std students refers to those who are obtaining upper primary or middle school education from any Government, Aided or Matriculation Schools.

Objectives

- i. To design theme based model for the select content in standard VIII English.
- ii. To access the effectiveness of content based instruction in English language teaching.
- iii. To find out the pre and post-test scores of control group students.
- iv. To find out the pre and post-test scores of experimental group students.
- v.

Hypotheses Of The Study

1. Control group and experimental group students do not differ in their gain scores.
2. Control group and experimental group students do not differ in their pre and post test scores
3. Experimental group students do not differ in their pre and post test scores

Research Method Adopted

The researcher had used the pre-test and post-test equivalent group design. In educational research, .Experimentation is the most scientifically sophisticated research method. It is defined as observation under controlled condition. Experimentation is therefore the name given to the type of educational research in which the investigator controls the educational factors to which a single or group is subjected during the period of inquiry and observes the resulting achievement. One must start the experiment with some measurement of the initial attainment of the group in the trait or ability to be influenced. The investigator, then subject the group to the experiment factor such as the particular method of teaching, for the duration of the experiment. At the end, the investigator applies a final test for the purpose of determining the gain in learning that has resulted from the application of the experiment.

Methodology adopted for the study:

- The static-group comparison design adopted for the present study. This design compares the status of a group that has received an experimental treatment with one that has not.
- Control group (30 Students) = pretest-----no treatment-----post test
- Experimental group (30 Students) = pretest-----treatment-----posttest

Sample Selection For The Study

The investigator purposively selected Government higher secondary school, S.Kollapatti at Salem district to serve as both experimental and control groups. There were 30

students in each group. In this study, a total number of 60 VIII standard students were chosen as samples.

Tools Used For The Study

For treatment the following methods were used

1. Simplified lesson plan for English content
2. Language oriented games (word building, past tense reading)
3. past tense songs
4. theme based models from the content (Issac Newton inventions, handouts, video clippings)

For the present study, the investigator prepared a standardized question paper from the prescribed content.

1. Fill in the blanks with suitable tense (20x1=20) [Sir Issac Newton –the ingenious Scientist ,paragraph)
2. Circle the past tense from the sentences (10x1=10)
3. Multiple choice question (20x1=20)

Collection Of Data

The data was collected from the pre and post test in the name of diagnostic and objective type questions were given just before and after the teaching program.

Statistical Technique

The collected data were statistically analyzed using “t” test to find out the significant difference between pre and post-test means and gain scores of both groups.

Analysis Of Data

The data on selected variables were analyzed and the obtained results are presented in Table I,II and III. Mean values of pre and post test and gain scores among select subjects are graphically represented in figure I and II.

Testing Hypothesis

Hypothesis-1

Control group and experimental group students do not differ in their gain scores

From the below table 1 the calculated “ t “ value is higher than the table value hence the null hypothesis is rejected. There is significant difference between the means of control and experimental group students in their gain scores.

Hypothesis-2

Control group and experimental group students do not differ in their pre and post test scores

From the below table 2 the calculated” t” value of pre test of control and experimental groups are not significant hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

The post test of experimental and control group students are significant at 0.05% level. Calculated t value is comparatively higher than the table value hence the null hypothesis is rejected. There is significant differences between post test scores of control group and experimental group students.

Hypothesis-3

Experimental group students do not differ in their pre and post test scores

Table-1

Showing the mean difference of gain scores of Control group and experimental group.

GROUP	N	MEAN	SD	t-value	Level of significance
Control group	30	41.66	16.37	7.47	Significant at 0.01 level
Experimental group	30	71.03	14.04		

Table-2

Showing the mean scores and, standard deviation of VIII standard students in pre-test and post-test of control and experimental group students

Students	Group	Pre-test		t value	Post-test		t value
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
VIII standard students	Control group	3.76	1.92	0.67	1.5	2.64	significant 4.70
	Experimental group	3.57	2.22		6.2	4.8	

Table-3

Showing the mean scores and, standard deviation of VIII standard students in pre-test and post-test of experimental group

Students	Group	Pre-test		Post-test		t value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
VIII standard students	Experimental group	3.57	2.22	6.2	4.8	2.73

Results And Discussion On Findings

The result of the study indicated that, there is a significant difference exists between the gain scores of control and experimental groups. Also there is a significant difference exists between the pre and post test scores of experimental group. Hence the researcher's null hypothesis rejected. Based on the results this study is highly effective for the students to be well versed in content as well as language.

This study will also be helpful for the primary students, they can learn from childhood so it became their habit. It will help them to proceed with their higher classes.

This study can be used for all the levels of school education as well as higher education level especially those who are hesitate the Second language learning will be benefited through this CBI instruction.

Educational Implications

There are many students from regional languages shifting to a second language for the development of communicative skills. This study focuses on the importance of communicative skills. The ever-changing society needs ever-growing students in all fields. So far, multilingualism culture renders its hands to develop a common language. For that, along with the content, second language development is possible. English Language

Enhancement skills. Generally, language learning has no boundaries. According to the usage of the language and emerging technology, the ever-growing vocabularies provide an opportunity to create naming words and onomatopoeia words. The language foundation hardly relies upon the skills of Listening, speaking, reading and writing. Nowadays, a lot of skills are to be obtained to get proficiency in language learning. Not only the LSRW but also body language play an important role in language learning. Most of the language studies were focused mainly on one particular skill or general skill. Very few studies were concentrated on all the basic skills of English. The two variables of the study cannot be separated as both focused on the enhancement of content and language.

Conclusion

This content based instruction is highly helpful for the learners. It creates interest towards learning. And theme based model make the students to participate actively in their class, content may be instructed through theme make them to come out with new ideas and they find their desire and they described it. They gained knowledge and interest of language learning and they are good in content learning too.

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